

TRANSLATION OF PROFESSIONAL PSYCHOLOGY WORDS FROM RUSSIAN INTO UZBEK

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ABSTRACT

*This article discusses the translation of professional
psychological words from Russian to Uzbek and gives
examples.*

INTRODUCTION

With independence on the threshold of the 21st century, Uzbekistan has become one of the fastest growing countries in the world. Youth is the main object and subject of further modernization of the country in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022 - 2026, put forward by the President of the country Sh.M. Mirziyoyev dated January 28, 2021 [1]. In conditions of independence, various opportunities have opened up for young people to realize their potential. At the same time, young people have become the object of various informational, psychological and ideological attacks from various forces. The formation of the ability to resist such attacks can be facilitated by the development of spirituality in general and the development of psychology as a science in particular. And psychology, as we know, deals with the development of the individual and society as a whole.

To increase psychological literacy and develop skills of psychological defense against various kinds of manipulation, it is necessary to actively develop psychological science in our country, create psychological centers and associations. These processes have already been carried out in recent years, but there is an objective need to provide the necessary scientific, educational and methodological literature and manuals in the Uzbek language.

This field of science is rapidly developing in our country and the problem of the lack of methods and manuals in the Uzbek language is still noticeable. In recent years, many publications devoted to theoretical aspects of psychology have been published. And experts pay great attention to topical issues of practical psychology.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this article, the authors analyzed some aspects of the translation of psychological techniques into the Uzbek language. Based on the results of the analysis, it was revealed:

Firstly, today there are not enough methods translated into Uzbek and adapted. This

fact influences the teaching of psychological science in the country's universities, the conduct of psychological work in various areas: preschool, school, in the field of correctional pedagogy, etc.

Universities mainly use books and manuals of foreign and Russian origin. Teachers are forced to translate various types of information to teach students. In recent years, rapid publication and production of domestic scientific and educational literature has begun.

Secondly, the connection between psychological and philological disciplines is underdeveloped. This is felt in the published works of psychologists, coursework and diploma works of students. The opinion of students is not taken into account. The current language barrier may worsen in the future if attention is not paid to language teaching in the country's schools.

Thirdly, there are not enough specialists involved in translating psychological literature. Translation work is carried out in a "handicraft" way, i.e. Translations are carried out by people who do not have special training, which affects the quality of the translation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The purpose of translation is to establish equivalence relations between the source and target text (so that both texts carry the same meaning). These restrictions include context, rules of grammar of the source language, writing traditions, its idioms, etc."

There are several main translation methods:

- Literal translation – the essence of the work is that all words are translated in a general sense, the literal context is not taken into account and the full word order of the original language is preserved. The purpose of such a translation is to clearly convey the idea of a specific text, as well as to preserve as close as possible the lexical composition and syntactic structure of the original language. If it becomes possible to leave the syntactic structure of the translated text or sentence in the target language, or to express it by similar means, then such work can be considered completed, and a literal translation does not require literary processing. This happens quite rarely, since the constructions of various languages have great differences, and constructions are often violated during literal translation.

- Literal translation - the essence of such work is that the grammatical structures of the original language are compared with the language into which they are being translated, the most similar ones are selected, and the translation is considered completed. A peculiarity of this work is that lexical words are translated separately without context.

- Accurate translation – consists in reproducing the most accurate meaning of the translated text and keeping the grammatical structures of the language into which it is translated within a narrow framework.

- Semantic translation is almost identical to exact translation, but its peculiarity is that words from the original language acquire a more aesthetic connotation when translated.

- Adaptation is a free-form translation, which is most often used to translate plays, comedies, etc. The characters remain, and the context is adapted in the translated version to the culture of the language of the given period.

- Free translation – translation of text without preserving the style, form or even content of the text.

- Idiomatic translation – the meaning of the text is preserved, but colloquialisms, idioms, and catchphrases that do not exist in the original appear, to which significant

advantage is given.

- Literary translation - in this type of work, specialists try to present the most accurate meaning of a word into the translated language, so that it is accessible to the reader.

The grammatical structure of an Uzbek sentence is very different from other, even closely related, languages. For example, sentence structure:

«В наше время огромное психологическое влияние на сознание и подсознание человека оказывают средства массовой информации (СМИ)». In Uzbek this sentence will sound like this: «Bizning davrimizda odamning ong va ong ostiga ommaviy axborot vositalari (OAV) ulkan psixologik ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda». This shows the opposite structure of the sentence in both languages. When translating from Russian, the grammatical structure of a sentence changes greatly. If you change parts of the sentence here, the meaning also changes.

When conducting psychodiagnostics of a psychological study, Russian-speaking subjects easily assimilate and understand the questions and instructions of the method, but unfortunately psychologists experience difficulties when working with respondents who speak only the Uzbek language. Therefore, at the present stage, the task of translating and adapting psychological methods into the Uzbek language is urgent.

As an example, we can use the Personality Accentuations questionnaire by Karl Leonhard, adapted into Russian [3]. The questionnaire consists of 10 scales, in accordance with the 10 types of accentuated personalities identified by Leonhard, and consists of 88 questions that must be answered "yes" or "no". One of the questions: «Трудно ли вам длительное время просидеть на стуле?» Here, a direct or literal translation is inappropriate, since the meaning of the question is clearly distorted: "Kursida sizga uzoq vaqt o'tirmoq qiyinmi?". Taking into account the mental characteristics of the Uzbek people, a semantic or free translation is used and the question should sound like this: «Bir joyda (note that the word used is «joyda - place», not «kursida») uzoq («vaqt» skipped) o'tirishga qiyinalasizmi?». This is due to the fact that in Europe and Russia they usually sit on a chair, on a sofa, on an armchair, and Uzbeks, in addition to a chair, also sit on a "kurpacha" (a national narrow long blanket-mattress) around a dastarkhan tablecloth.

CONCLUSION

To summarize, we can say that when translating psychological methods and scientific or educational literature, one must use semantic or free translation, since direct translation does not provide a certain accuracy. The main problem is the distortion of the meaning of the translated methods. Methods must be translated by highly qualified specialists from the original source (language)..

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